

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SELF-REINFORCED POLYESTER DOUBLE COVERED UNCOMMINGLED YARN COMPOSITES

C. M. Wu^{1*}, C. T. Tsai², C. H. Hsu¹, J. Y. Lee¹

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Taipei 10607, Taiwan, R.O.C.

² Department of Fiber and Composite Materials, Feng-Chia University, Taichung 40724, Taiwan, R.O.C.

* Corresponding author (cmwu@mail.ntust.edu.tw)

ABSTRACT

Self-reinforced PET (srPET) composites composed of double covered uncommingled yarn were developed by cowrap spinning method. The influence of woven structures on the impregnation quality of laminates is investigated by characterizing the mechanical properties and failure behaviors of the srPET composites. The srPET laminates with plain structure demonstrate the best tensile and flexural responses, whereas twill weaving structure exhibits the highest impact energy absorption (857 J/m).

Keywords: Polyester, self-reinforced composites, uncommingled yarn, mechanical properties,

1 Introduction

There is a growing interest to either improve the methods for recycling and reusing existing composites, or develop new and intrinsically more suitable composites. The creation of self-reinforced polymer composites (srPCs, also termed single polymer composites or all-polymer composites) is an excellent alternative to traditional fiber-reinforced composites since both the reinforcing and the continuous phases are polymers with the same chemical composition [1-3]. These polymers can be entirely melted down at the end of their product life for recycling. The srPC possesses many advantages and features, such as thermoform ability, high stiffness, high tensile strength, outstanding impact resistance at low density; it contains no glass, etc. In 1975, Capiati and Porter initially developed polyethylene/polyethylene composite and introduced the concept of srPCs [4]. Ward et al. [5-9] further

developed this type of composite material by using the "hot compaction" technique. Following this study, opening literatures report a large number of various techniques and materials. The literature contains numerous studies on the preparation of polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate, polymethyl methacrylate, liquid crystal copolymer, polylactic acid, and polyamide srPCs [1-9]. The main challenge when producing a srPC material is combining fiber and matrix into one composite. Various fabrication methods such as hot compaction, overheating, co-extrusion, film stacking, and traditional melt or powder impregnation can produce the srPCs [1-3]. The use of commingled yarns is one of the more promising routes for producing structural thermoplastic composites. The textile processes available enable faster manufacturing and tailoring of the fiber architecture of preform. As the polymer flow distance for impregnation is reduced when the matrix is already commingled with reinforcing fibers, the time for impregnation or the need for high applied pressure are reduced, leading to an improvement in impregnation and even distribution, and reduction in manufacturing cost. Moreover, compared to other intermediate product forms such as preimpregnated tows or powder-impregnated fiber bundles, the flexible cowrap spinning yarns can easily be converted into highly drapable textile fabric preforms, reducing the possibility of wrinkles during the formation of complex shapes.

The use of textile reinforced thermoplastic composites in high performance light weight structural parts offers advantages compared to conventional constructions, particularly, in complex light weight applications and the function-integrating multi-material design. Hybrid yarn

manufacturing has been developed recently for rapid and cost-effective processing of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites [10-13].

A preferred yarn structure is one in which the reinforcing fibers are straight and parallel to the yarn axis. A spinning method developed in the late 1970s, known as hollow spindle wrap spinning, can be used to produce such a yarn. Wrap spinning machines are commercially available for some specialized products, including knitting yarns and carpet yarns. The wrap spun yarn consists of twistless staple fibers wrapped by a filament or a fine thread. The wrapping filament applies the fiber-to-fiber pressure that is required to create the friction between the fibers and thus the yarn strength [10-13]. Because of the lower fiber-to-fiber pressure generated by the wrapping filament in comparison with that generated by the twist, wrap spun yarns generally are lower in tensile strength and are less compact than the ring spun yarns at their optimal twist level. Wrap spinning is generally cheaper to run than ring spinning for the production of coarse count yarns.

Because of the very short flow paths of the viscous thermoplastic melt, commingled yarns offer an ideal opportunity to achieve short cycle times. However, it was reported that the mechanical properties of the composites are strongly influenced by the hybrid yarn impregnation homogeneity, the unidirectional/textile subassemblies, the sizing on the reinforcing fiber, and the consolidation processing conditions. A number of studies have been directed towards manufacturing of commingled yarn, properties of composites made from commingled yarn and effects of processing conditions on impregnation, consolidation behavior. Therefore, cowrap spinning commingled methods will open up a broader prospect for development of thermoplastic resin composites, but there are not yet been applied in the development of srPCs.

Therefore, the objective of this work is the investigation of self-reinforced PET (srPET) composites by using double covered uncommingled PET yarns and their fabrics. Three kinds of woven structures, plain, twill, and basket weave were employed. The influence of the fabric's architectures and processing conditions on the tensile, flexural and impact properties of srPET composites were studied.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Commercially high tenacity PET multifilaments, with a melting point of 262°C (as shown in Fig. 1), were used as reinforcement due to their higher strength and modulus. The PET yarn consists of 1000 denier multifilament bundles with tenacity of 9.2 g/denier and elongation of 15.1 %. Copolymerized PET (mPET) multifilaments with a melting temperature of 224°C (as shown in Fig. 1) were used as the matrix. The mPET yarn consists of 320 denier multifilament bundles with tenacity of 4.7 g/denier and elongation of 30.4 %. They were used to produce the uncommingled yarns for producing weaved fabric.

The viscosity was studied by capillary rheometry (Rheo-tester 1501, Göttfert, Germany) to understand the flow and impregnation behaviors of the mPET matrix. Fig. 2 displays the viscosity behaviors of the polyester resin at testing temperature of 230 to 250 °C. High viscosity, 4000 Pa·s, was measured at testing temperature of 230 °C, and then dropped to 700 Pa·s at 235 °C. The viscosity decreases with temperature increasing and reaches to equilibrium at temperature higher than 235 °C. The average viscosities measured at 238 to 250 °C are between 300 to 150 Pa·s. Such high viscosity in the polyester resin is about three orders higher than that of conventional thermoset resin (0.2 Pa·s). The conventional thermosetting processing methods are thus not utilized for the polyester resin and have to develop some others.

2.2 Sample Preparation

PET and mPET yarn with designed 50/50 volume fraction were used to prepare the double covered uncommingled yarns (DCUY) (as shown in Fig 3a) by hollow spindle spinning machine. The high tenacity PET multifilament yarn was used as reinforcing core yarn, and the mPET multifilament yarn was used as wrapping material for the linear cowrap spinning yarn preforms. The stability of the yarn mainly depends on the binding yarn and twist introduced by the spinning. The mPET filaments served as carrier for the PET multifilament yarn during processing and became the polymer matrix in the final composites, which prevented impregnation difficulty and damage to the reinforcing PET multifilament yarn during processing. To get an even distribution of fiber and thermoplastic resin in preforms and designed fiber content (50 wt%), the

main spinning parameters (hollow spindle twist: 776 T/m and hollow spindle rotational speed: 5554 U/min.) were optimized.

DCUY was used as a feed material for the production of three kinds of woven structure (plain, twill, and basket weave) preforms in this study. Figure 3a shows the surface of cowrap spinning yarn, the wrapped angle between mPET multifilaments and reinforcing PET core yarn axis was demonstrated and determined by the cowrap spinning parameters. By changing the cowrap spinning parameters, different reinforced PET fiber content could be achieved. Then, the cowrap spinning yarns, as warp and weft yarns, were woven on a rapier weave machine, designing the structure (plain, twill, and basket) and weaving density (warp/weft) of fabric according to the actual requirements. Table 1 shows the weave density for various woven structure of fabrics. Fig. 3b shows the appearance of the srPET preform and the actual reinforcing fiber volume fraction is 47 % in fabrics. This study presents a modified film stacking technique to produce high quality impregnated and void free srPET composites. Shrinkage problems may be encountered when heating the dry fabrics and yarns. To prevent PET fiber shrinkage and relaxation during the heat consolidating processing, the fabric was first subjected to a thermal setting for 3 min. at 195 °C. Single laminae were prepared by hot pressed the preform at 240 °C for 1min under a pressure of 50 Kg/cm² followed by quenching in water together with the covering of Teflon films. srPET laminates (as shown in Fig. 3c) were prepared by stacking four layers of laminae at 235 °C for 3 min. at a pressure of 100 Kg/cm² followed by slow cooling to room temperature and demolded. It is worth to note that the difficulty of impregnation is largely improved due to good compatibility between the constituents in the srPET composites. The melted mPET matrices did not run off the mold due to high viscosity of the resin. Thus, the fiber volume fractions of the srPET composites were approximately 47 %.

2.3 Mechanical Tests

A universal test machine (AG-100kNX, Shimadzu, Japan) was used to perform the tensile test for lamina and composite and for three-point bending flexural tests at room temperature according to ASTM D638 (type I) and according to D3039 and

D790, respectively. Tensile specimens cut from the prepared srPET samples were 250 × 25 × 2 mm³ in normal dimensions, and were clamped over an area of 50 × 25 mm² at each end, leaving a gauge length of 150 mm. Aluminum tabs were glued onto the ends of the specimens to aid gripping areas. The grip pressure was hydraulically controlled. The testing crosshead speeds were 5 mm/min for the tensile test. The specimen size for the three-point bending test is 100 × 25.4 × 2 mm³. A span length of 64 mm assured a span-to-depth ratio of 32, and crosshead speeds of 3.4 mm/min were adopted. The Izod impact test was performed at room temperature according to ASTM D256 on a pendulum impact tester (CPI, Atlas electric devices, USA) at an impact energy of 5.4 J. The impact velocity used was 3.4 m/s. The dimensions of the Izod impact specimen were 63.5 × 12.7 × 2 mm³, and the specimens were provided with a notch having a depth of 2.7 ± 0.2 mm. All the mechanical properties reported represent the average value of at least five readings. Damaged specimens were inspected by stereo microscopy (S422L, Microtech, Taipei, Taiwan) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM; S3000, Hitachi, Japan) to understand their failure modes. Prior to the SEM observations the samples were mounted on aluminum stubs and sputter coated with a thin layer of gold to avoid electrical charging. SEM micrographs were taken at a 10 kV acceleration voltage at various magnifications.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Consolidation Temperature and Lamina Quality

The mechanical properties of a laminated composite are strongly influenced by lamina quality. For a viscous thermoplastic matrix, lamina quality depends on the number of voids, extent of impregnation, and extent of degradation of the matrix. In general, the flow distance and pressure distribution in lamina are smaller and more uniform than those of thick laminated composites. The holding time for lamina consolidation can be reduced, which also allows the consolidation temperature to be increased. As we know, impregnation of srPET composites is governed by consolidation temperature and consolidation time. Higher temperature and shorter time are recommended for lower viscosity of the polyester

resin and avoid resin degradation. Therefore, it is interesting to determine the optimal consolidation temperature condition.

Figure 2 shows the typical tensile stress-strain curves of srPET laminae (twill woven structure) at different consolidation temperatures. The curves for srPET laminae show significant yielding and post-yield strain hardening, which are indicative of its reinforcing effect and structural homogeneity. Good tensile properties (steep curve) of the laminae prepared at higher consolidation temperatures indicate that the srPET lamina structure was more compact at higher consolidation temperatures, with lower viscosity and better impregnation. The slope between the yield point and the failure point (called the post-yield modulus) represents the reinforcing efficiency of the srPET laminae. The post-yield modulus is sensitive to the thermal degradation of the polyester matrix and the resulting poor interfacial adhesion [33]. A brittle type failure was found in the samples consolidated at 250°C. The post-yield modulus and the tensile strength are similar for consolidation temperatures at 235 and 245°C. Higher tensile modulus and lower strain were found in srPET laminae prepared at 245°C compared to that prepared at 235°C. This increase was on account of adequate impregnation at higher consolidation temperatures. The yielding elongation for the srPET laminae prepared at 235 and 245°C is approximately 3 % which is similar to the failure strain of the samples consolidated at 250°C.

To understand the tensile failure mechanism, the post-test specimens were examined and shown in Fig. 5. It was found that the laminae prepared at different consolidation temperatures exhibited similar types of failure. However, there were some differences between the reinforcing yarns and the polymer matrix. In the case of srPET lamina prepared at 250 °C (Fig 5c), the reinforcing yarns were melted and well incorporated with the mPET matrices. The tensile modulus thus reached the highest value 2.48 GPa which were respectively 43 % and 12 % higher than the values obtained at 235 and 240 °C. The high modulus results can be attributed to better impregnation and reinforcing structural integrity caused by good bonding. A brittle breaking failure was found in the samples consolidated at 250 °C. Due to the vanishment of PET reinforcing yarns for forming an integration of

resin buck, the sample can bear higher tensile loading until the crack initiated. However, cracks propagate and crossover throughout the specimen easily without any retardation by the reinforcing fibers. By contrast, the reinforcing yarns were well observed and bonded with the mPET matrices in the sample prepared at 235 and 245°C. Fiber putout and breakage were observed in these two samples. A greater amount of de-bonding was observed in the samples prepared at 235 °C (Fig 5a). This was due to poor impregnation between the matrix and the PET yarn at the low temperature. However, there was substantially less de-bonding in the srPET composites prepared at 240°C (Fig 5b), resulting in the adequate impregnation and reinforcing structural integrity expected at this consolidation temperature.

The tensile properties were determined from Fig 5 and summarizes in Table 2. The tensile elongation of the srPET laminae was approximately 35-43 % for laminae prepared at 235 to 240 °C. However, premature fiber breakage was found in the srPET laminae prepared at 250 °C. Such breakage was believed to be caused by the loss of reinforcing PET fiber structure and degradation of the mPET matrices. These two factors all contributed to the embrittlement of the laminate. Comparing the tensile properties of samples with similar failure modes prepared at 235 and 240 °C. The srPET lamina consolidated at 240°C exhibited higher tensile modulus of 2.21 GPa, and a tensile strength of 79.8 MPa, which were respectively 27 % and 5 % higher than the values obtained at 235 °C. Therefore, the optimal temperature for manufacturing lamina was found to be 240°C and the same temperature was utilized to prepare materials for srPET composite evaluation.

3.1 Tensile properties

Observing the tensile stress-strain curves of the srPET composites as shown in Fig. 6, exhibited significant yielding and post-yield strain hardening, which are indicative of the reinforcing effect and structural homogeneity of the srPET composites. The mechanical properties of srPET laminates including tensile strength, tensile modulus, tensile elongation, yield strength, and post-yield modulus were summarized in Table 3. No visible difference on the initial slope was observed which indicated the tensile modulus does not affect by the woven structures (as shown in Table 3). However, the slope

between the yield points to the failure point (called the post-yield modulus) was largely influenced by the woven structures. The basket weaving structure represents the highest post-yield modulus (185 MPa), follow by twill (98 MPa) and plain structure was the worst (71 MPa). On the contrary, the basket weaving structure shows the lowest tensile elongation (32 %), follow by twill (50 %) and plain structure was the highest (55 %). This result agrees with those of study on flax/polypropylene composites prepared by cowrap spinning method [11]. The results showed that the friction and compressibility and the fabric structure effects were not negligible, which relates directly with the influence of the cowrap yarn properties on the friction behavior and intercross points of warp and weft yarns in different structure fabrics. The main reason for these differences was due to a different fabric structure, different numbers of interwoven yarn in warp and weft, the varying crook degree of flexion, and the angle of woven yarn. The results indicate that basket weaving structure exhibit the highest resistance for crack propagation. In plain fabric, there were more intercross points and crook degree of wrap and weft yarns in periodic unit cell than twill and basket, so the clamp points were more, which results in more clamp force on yarns at the intercross points during stretching and had more elongation. As a result, the plain structure displays the highest yield strength and yield elongation (62.1 MPa, 5.00%), whereas twill and basket weaving structure exhibits similar but lower values (around 37 MPa and 2%). Consideration of both effects on the yielding and post yielding behavior, the plain structure shows the highest tensile strength (96.3 MPa), follow by basket weaving and twill structure was the worst (81.6 MPa). It is worthy to note that the tensile properties for the srPET laminae and laminates (twill) as shown in Table 2 and 3 are quite similar and prove that the tensile properties of laminates can be represented by that of laminae.

3.2 Flexural properties

Figure 7 shows the typical flexural stress-strain curves of srPET laminates prepared by various weaving structures. The srPET composites did not collapse within the crosshead limit. This reveals the prevention ability from crack propagation by the reinforcing woven fabric. Examining the appearance of failed specimens, as shown in Fig. 6, we did not find any visible failures in the bent srPET samples,

which demonstrate its highly tough character. The flexural properties were similar for the twill and plain weaving structural composites. The basket structure srPET samples exhibited the worst flexural properties. The flexural properties of the srPET composites, as shown in Table 4, demonstrated that a highest flexural modulus and strength were 3.6 GPa and 74.4 MPa for plain structure. However, the srPET composites with basket weaving structure exhibited the worst flexural modulus (2.7 GPa) and strength (61.8 MPa) which were 33% and 19% decreasing as compare to the plain fabric composites.

3.3 Impact properties

The notched Izod impact energy of the srPET composites were listed in Table 4. The impact energy ranged from 484 to 857 J/m for the srPET samples prepared by different weaving fabrics which is similar to the best srPET sample obtained in our previous study (854 J/m) [14-15]. The absorbed impact energy for srPET laminates prepared by DUCY shows 30 folds enhancement than that of pure polyester resin (28 J/m). The impacted srPET composites prepared by the twill and plain weaving structural fabrics did not break apart and showed tensile and compressive failures in two sides of the impacted specimen (Fig. 7a and 7b). When an impactor encountered the srPET specimen, fiber-bundle breakage occurred around the notched side first, whereas the compressive force increased on the other side of the specimen. Owing to the laminated nature and integrity of the woven fabric architecture, fiber-bundle breakage occurred near the notch area and subsequent extensive delamination occurred along the interlaminar interface. However, as shown in Fig. 7c, the srPET composites prepared by basket weaving structural fabric displayed break apart failure and resulted in the lowest impact energy. It can be attributed to the larger gap between two interweaving points which create a weak path. A severe fiber pullout and breakage can be observed in the tensile side of the basket samples. By contrast, a severe compressive shearing failure (Fig. 7d) was found on the compressive side of the plain and twill samples that accompany the fiber breakage (kink and buckle), the matrix crush, and delaminations.

4. Conclusion

Commingled yarns of reinforcing and thermoplastic fibers offer a potential for low-cost manufacturing of

complex-shape composite parts, due to reduced impregnation times and applied pressures during processing. Self-reinforced polyester composites composed of double covered uncommingled yarn were developed by cowrap spinning method. The DCUY were used to weave into fabric preforms and molded by film stacking technique. Experimental results showed that the srPET composites display significant improvement in their tensile, flexural, and impact properties. The fabric structures affecting the mechanical properties of self-reinforced PET (srPET) composites were investigated and reported. The tensile properties of laminates can be represented by that of laminae. The srPET laminates with plain structure shows the best tensile and flexural responses, whereas twill weaving structure exhibits the highest impact energy absorption (857 J/m). The absorbed impact energy of the srPET composites prepared by DCUY methods is similar to the best srPET sample obtained in our previous study by film stacking technique and shows 30 folds enhancement than that of pure polyester resin.

Acknowledgements

Part of this work is financially supported from the National Science Council of Taiwan, ROC, under contract number NSC 101 -2622 -E -011 -023 -CC3.

References

[1] A. Pegoretti “Trends in composite materials: The challenge of single-polymer composites“. *Express Polymer Letters*, Vol. 1, pp 710, 2007.
 [2] K.P. Matabola, A.R. DeVries, F.S. Moolman, A.S. Luyt “Single polymer composites: A review“. *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 44, pp 6213-6222, 2009.
 [3] Á. Kmetty, T. Barany, J. Karger-Kocsis “Self-reinforced polymeric materials: A review“. *Progress in Polymer Science*, Vol. 35, pp 1288-1310, 2010.
 [4] N. J. Capiati, R. S. Porter “The concept of one polymer composites modelled with high density polyethylene“. *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 10, pp 1671–1677, 1975.

[5] P. J. Hine, I. M. Ward, M. I. A. Maaty, R. H. Olley, D. C. Basset “The hot compaction of 2-dimensional woven melt spun high modulus polyethylene fibers“. *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 35, pp 5091–5099, 2000.
 [6] P. J. Hine, I. M. Ward, N. D. Jordan, R. H. Olley, D. C. Basset “The hot compaction behaviour of woven oriented polypropylene fibres and tapes. I. Mechanical properties“. *Polymer*, Vol. 44, pp 1117–1131, 2003.
 [7] P. J. Hine, I. M. Ward “Hot compaction of woven poly(ethylene terephthalate) multifilaments“. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 91, pp 2223–2233, 2004.
 [8] I. M. Ward, P. J. Hine “The science and technology of hot compaction“. *Polymer*, Vol. 45, pp 1413–1427, 2004.
 [9] P. J. Hine, R. H. Olley, I. M. Ward “The use of interleaved films for optimising the production and properties of hot compacted, self reinforced polymer composites“. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, pp 1413–1421, 2008.
 [10] N. Svensson, R. Shishoo, M. Gilchrist “Manufacturing of thermoplastic composites from commingled yarns- A review“. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composites Materials*, Vol. 11, pp 22-56, 1998.
 [11] J. Jiang, N. Chen “Preforms and composites manufactured by novel flex/polypropylene cowrap spinning method“. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 46, pp 2097-2109, 2012.
 [12] E. Maeder, J. Rausch, N. Schmidt “Commingled yarns- Processing aspects and tailored surfaces of polypropylene/glass composites“. *Composites. Part A*, Vol. 39, pp 612-623, 2008.
 [13] T. Gobi Kannan, C. M. Wu, K. B. Cheng “Effect of different knitted structure on the mechanical properties and damage behavior of flax/PLA (Poly Lactic acid) double covered uncommingled yarn composites“. *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 43, pp 2836-2842, 2012.
 [14] J. C. Chen, C. M. Wu, F. C. Pu, C. H. Chiu “Fabrication and mechanical properties of self-reinforced poly(ethylene terephthalate) composites“. *Express Polymer Letters*, Vol. 5, pp 228-237, 2010.
 [15] C. M. Wu, C. Y. Chang, C. C. Wang, C. Y. Lin “Optimum consolidation of all-polyester woven fabric-reinforced composite laminates by film stacking“. *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 33, pp 245-252, 2012.

Table 1. Weaving density and pattern of the reinforcing fabrics for the srPET composites

Woven structures		Plain	Basket	Twill
weaving density (warp/weft)	(fabric)	33x20	42x23	41x26
	(composites)	38x23	49x32	50x33
Weaving pattern				

Fig. 1 DSC Thermograms of the polyester resin and the reinforcing PET yarn.

Fig. 2 The viscosity behaviors of the polyester resin at testing temperatures of 230 to 250 °C studied by capillary rheometry under various shear rates.

Fig. 3 The appearance of (a) the double covered uncommingled yarns (DCUY), (b) Fabric preform, and (c) its srPET composites.

Table 2. Tensile properties for the srPET laminae prepared at different consolidation temperatures.

Consolidated Temperature	235 °C	245 °C	250 °C
Tensile strength (MPa)	75.86±3.99	79.82±4.08	43.74±5.11
Tensile strain (%)	42.85±1.23	35.42±3.31	3.18±1.97
Tensile modulus (GPa)	1.74±1.17	2.21±1.65	2.48±1.29

Fig. 4 Typical tensile stress-strain curves of the srPET laminae at different consolidation temperatures.

Fig. 5 Typical tensile failure images for srPET laminae consolidated at (a) 235 °C, (b) 245 °C, (c) 250 °C.

Fig. 6 Typical tensile stress-strain curves of the srPET laminates with different weaving structures.

Table 3. Tensile properties for the srPET composites with various woven structures

Woven structures	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Elongation [%]	Post-yield modulus [MPa]	Yield strength [MPa]	Intercross points (#/in ²)
Plain	96.3±5.5	3.02±0.25	54.7±0.8	70.7±3.5	62.1	437
Basket	91.5±9.0	3.00±0.17	31.6±1.3	184.9±14.8	37.6	193
Twill	81.6±0.2	2.98±0.15	50.0±7.6	97.5±5.1	36.0	407

Fig. 7 Typical flexural stress-strain curves of the srPET laminates with different weaving structures.

Fig. 8 Typical flexural sample of the srPET laminates (a) before and (b) after flexural test.

Table 4. Flexural and Impact properties for the srPET composites with various woven structures

Woven structures	Flexural strength [MPa]	Flexural modulus [GPa]	Flexural deflection [%]	Impact energy [J/m]
Plain	74.4±4.3	3.56±0.21	3.46±0.13	608±24
Basket	61.8±6.5	2.43±0.31	4.13±2.57	484±20
Twill	72.4±7.2	3.55±0.07	3.68±1.55	857±32

Fig. 9 Typical impact failure of the srPET laminates for different (a) plain, (b) twill, (c) basket structures, and (d) the failure at compressive side for twill structure samples.